

NORMAL-/SHEAR-DECOHESIVE DAMAGE OF ADHESIVELY BONDED JOINTS AT ROOM/CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURES

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1 Introduction

It is well known that an adhesively bonded joints (ABJ) is fabricated using a combination of two or more (non-) metallic materials and adhesives. The ABJ is frequently adopted in various industrial structures, especially cryogenic industrial fields because of its superior material advantages, such as excellent bonding capacity, thermal barring capability, light weight, and ease of fabrication [1].

In order to design/manufacture the robust the ABJ, the mechanical behavior (i.e., nonlinear material behavior) of the ABJ under room/cryogenic temperatures must be evaluated in terms of decohesive damage incidents regarding to normal/shear loadings. In the present study, therefore, a series of pull-off and lap-shear tests are performed for the ABJ. Mechanical properties as well as the decohesive damage phenomenon are summarized in a quantitative manner. On the basis of the insights obtained from the experiments, a temperature-dependent constitutive model is proposed using a modification of the Ramberg–Osgood equation.

maintained from 73 K to ambient temperature using the cryogenic chamber. Fig. 2 shows the pull-off and lap-shear test specimens and schematic of the adhesive lamination of the ABJ. These were fabricated according to standards of ASTM and guide of Gaztransport & Technigaz. The epoxy adhesive is green (XB 5032 A/B, HUNTSMAN), and the polyurethane (PU) adhesive is grey (XPU 18411 A/B, ATO).

Fig. 1 Experimental apparatus (left) and experimental setup for pull-off test (right)

2 Experimental Apparatus and Results

2.1 Experimental Apparatus

A series of pull-off and lap-shear tests for two types of adhesives used for the fabrication of the ABJ were performed in order to compare the respective cryogenic performance of the adhesives. Epoxy and polyurethane adhesives were adopted as the adhesive materials for the ABJ. All of the tests were performed under low-temperature environments ranging from 110 to 293 K. A universal testing machine equipped with a cryogenic chamber was used for the parametric investigation (see Fig. 1). The designed test temperature ranges were

Fig. 2 Pull-off (left) and lap-shear (middle) test specimens and schematic of adhesive lamination (right)

2.2 Design of Experiments

As previously mentioned, two types of ABJ are frequently adopted in industrial fields. The material behaviour, including the debonding failure characteristics, of these types of ABJ is the primary subject of this paper. The two types of lamination structures are described in Table 1. The test scenarios were categorised into pull-off and lap-shear cases, and they are summarised in Tables 2 and 3. Each test was performed under varying temperatures (293, 163, and 110 K). In order to ascertain the repeatability of the test results, the tests in each case were performed seven times.

Table 1 Description of lamination types

Type of ABJ	Description
Type A	Polyurethane + Flexible triplex + Epoxy + Rigid triplex + Polyurethane
Type B	Polyurethane + Flexible triplex + Polyurethane + Rigid triplex + Polyurethane

Table 2 Test case for the pull-off test

Title of test	Type of ABJ	Temperature (K)	Adhesion area (mm ²)
Pull-off test	Type A	293	121.7
	Type A	163	121.7
	Type A	110	121.7
	Type B	293	121.7
	Type B	163	121.7
	Type B	110	121.7

Table 3 Test case for the lap-shear test

Title of test	Type of ABJ	Temperature (K)	Adhesion area (mm ²)
Lap-shear test	Type A	293	2500
	Type A	163	2500
	Type A	110	2500
	Type B	293	2500
	Type B	163	2500
	Type B	110	2500

2.3 Test Results and Discussion

Figs. 3 to 6 show the debonded surface and the stress and strain relationship obtained from the pull-off and lap-shear tests at each temperature. In the present study, the normal and shear stresses are mean stresses, i.e., the stress is simply calculated according to applied force divided by the adhesion area. The obtained test results of each adhesive according to temperature and loading direction are discussed in Tables 4 and 5.

(a) Type A, 293K

(b) Type A, 163K

(c) Type A, 110K

(d) Type B, 293K

(e) Type B, 163K

(f) Type B, 110K

Fig. 3 Photographs of the debonded surface of the pull-off test specimen

3 Constitutive Model

The temperature-dependent modified constitutive model which is based on Ramberg-Osgood [2] is proposed as follows:

$$\varepsilon, \gamma = \frac{\sigma, \tau(T)}{E, G(T)} + \left\langle \frac{|\sigma, \tau(T)| - \sigma_Y, \tau_Y(T)}{E', G'(T)} \right\rangle^{n(T)} \text{sgn}(\sigma, \tau) \quad (1)$$

with $\sigma, \tau(T) = \sigma_s, \tau_s(T)$,

where σ_Y/τ_Y is the normal/shear yield stress, E'/G' is the normal/shear stress coefficient, n/m is the normal/shear softening coefficient, σ_s/τ_s is the normal/shear plastic threshold stress, and $\langle \rangle$ are Macaulay parentheses. Table 6 lists the material properties of Eq. (1).

Fig. 4 Photographs of the debonded surface of the lap-shear test specimen

Fig. 5 Relationship between normal stress and strain in the pull-off test

Fig. 6 Relationship between shear stress and strain in the lap-shear test

Table 4 Obtained test results of each ABJ according to normal loading

Type of ABJ	Room temperature
Type A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The debonding occurred between the epoxy adhesive and the flexible/rigid triplex in approximately 50% of the cases. Nearly half of the debonding cases occurred between the polyurethane adhesive and the flexible/rigid triplex. This means that the normal bonding strength of both adhesives is nearly the same. This can be seen in Fig. 5. The debonded surface is very clear and there is no tearing of the epoxy adhesive.
Type B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All of the debonding occurred between the polyurethane adhesive and the flexible/rigid triplex. The debonded surface is very clear and there is no tearing of the polyurethane adhesive.
Type of ABJ	Cryogenic temperature
Type A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All of the debonding occurred between the epoxy adhesive and the flexible/rigid triplex. This means that the normal bonding strength of polyurethane adhesive is greater than that of epoxy adhesive. As in the room temperature case of both Type A and Type B, the debonded surface is very clear and there is no tearing of the epoxy adhesive. It is interesting that the normal strain of Type A is almost unaffected by temperature. Only an increase of the normal stress is observed in Type A.
Type B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As in the room temperature case, all of the debonding occurred between the polyurethane adhesive and the flexible/rigid triplex. However, the debonded surface is not clear, and there is tearing of the polyurethane adhesive. It is believed that the adhesion strength of the polyurethane adhesive at cryogenic temperatures under normal loading is stronger than it is in the other cases. This can be seen in Fig. 5.
Overall discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As the temperature decreases, the elastic stiffness/tensile strength increases. As the temperature decreases, the polyurethane adhesive exhibits normal strength that is higher than that of epoxy adhesive. Epoxy adhesive gives almost equal values of normal strain for all of the test temperatures. However, the fracture strain of the polyurethane adhesive increases as the temperature decreases.

The ten temperature-dependent parameters obtained from Eq. (1) can be represented as a linearized function of the temperature-dependent material coefficient, as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} E, G(T) \\ \sigma_Y, \tau_Y(T) \\ E', G'(T) \\ \sigma_T, \tau_T(T) \\ n, m(T) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} E_0, G_0 \\ \sigma_{Y0}, \tau_{Y0} \\ E'_0, G'_0 \\ \sigma_{T0}, \tau_{T0} \\ n_0, m_0 \end{Bmatrix} + T^* \begin{Bmatrix} a_1, b_1 \\ a_2, b_2 \\ a_3, b_3 \\ a_4, b_5 \\ a_5, b_5 \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

Table 5 Obtained test results of each ABJ according to shear loading

Type of ABJ	Room temperature
Type A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The debonding occurred between the polyurethane adhesive and the flexible/rigid triplex. From the test results, it can be inferred that the bonding capacities of the epoxy adhesive are stronger than those of the polyurethane adhesive at room temperature under shear loading. The debonded surface was very clear and no tearing was observed.
Type B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As in the Type A room temperature case, the debonding occurred between the polyurethane adhesive and the flexible/rigid triplex. From the test results of both cases at room temperature, it was found that the adhesion strength in both cases was the same. This can be seen in Fig. 6.
Type of ABJ	Cryogenic temperature
Type A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All of the debonding occurred between the epoxy adhesive and the flexible/rigid triplex. The debonded surface was rough, and it was especially rough at 110 K. The epoxy adhesive was frozen and broken between flexible and rigid triplexes, and the broken pieces of adhesive were attached to these triplexes. In addition, the shear stress rapidly increased. It seems that the frozen adhesive increased the bonding capacities under shear loading. It is also interesting that the shear strain of Type A was almost unaffected by temperature, as was seen in the results of the Type A pull-off test. An increase of the shear stress was also observed in Type A.
Type B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All of the debonding occurred between the polyurethane adhesive and the flexible/rigid triplex. The debonded surface was rough, and it was especially rough at 110 K, as in the Type A cryogenic temperature case. The polyurethane adhesive was also frozen and broken between flexible and rigid triplexes, and the broken pieces of adhesive were attached to these triplexes. However, the broken pieces of the polyurethane adhesive were larger than those of the epoxy adhesive. This indicates that the shear stress of the polyurethane adhesive is larger than that of the epoxy adhesive, as shown in Fig. 6.
Overall discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The shear elastic stiffness is almost unaffected by temperature; however, as the temperature decreases, a rapid increase of inelastic material behaviour is observed. As the temperature decreases, the polyurethane adhesive exhibits shear strength that is higher than that of the epoxy adhesive. Epoxy adhesive gives almost the same value of shear strain for all of the test temperatures. However, the fracture strain of the polyurethane adhesive increases as the temperature decreases, as in the result of the pull-off test.

$$T^* = \frac{T - T_{\text{ROOM}}}{T_{\text{ABS}} - T_{\text{ROOM}}}, \quad (3)$$

where subscript 0 indicates the initial value of each material parameter, a_i and b_i are the material parameters, T^* is the reference temperature, T_{ABS} is the absolute zero temperature, and T_{ROOM} is the room temperature, i.e., 293 K. Table 7 lists the material parameters of Eqs. (2) and (3).

Table 6 Material properties of the ABJ

Adhesive	Temp. (K)	E (MPa)	σ_Y (MPa)	E' (MPa)	σ_T (MPa)	n
Epoxy	293	146	4.62	-	-	-
	163	418	12.3	-	-	-
	110	440	12.6	-	-	-
PU	293	140	3.34	-	-	-
	163	324	13.1	-	-	-
	110	362	16.2	-	-	-
Adhesive	Temp. (K)	G (MPa)	τ_Y (MPa)	G' (MPa)	τ_T (MPa)	m
Epoxy	293	186	0.88	181	5.21	0.63
	163	193	0.94	1582	9.68	0.49
	110	527	1.16	1888	15.3	0.34
PU	293	108	1.14	470	5.36	0.62
	163	155	1.20	1259	23.6	0.52
	110	432	0.96	1434	26.7	0.48

Table 7 Material parameters of the ABJ

Adhesive	E_0 (MPa)	σ_{Y0} (MPa)	E'_0 (MPa)	σ_{T0} (MPa)	n_0
Epoxy	157.51	4.99	-	-	-
PU	144.79	3.45	-	-	-
Adhesive	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
Epoxy	497.16	13.62	-	-	-
PU	366.34	20.84	-	-	-
Adhesive	G_0 (MPa)	τ_{Y0} (MPa)	G'_0 (MPa)	τ_{T0} (MPa)	n_0
Epoxy	55.00	0.85	215.34	4.72	1.58
PU	48.75	1.17	488.99	5.92	1.62
Adhesive	b_1	b_2	b_3	b_4	b_5
Epoxy	197.38	0.39	2811.03	15.00	1.13
PU	140.08	-0.21	1586.55	35.45	0.71

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